

Table 4. STEAM education, environmental ethics, and curriculum framework acquisitions in Portuguese curriculum policy documents for compulsory schooling (ages 10–14).

Field	Acquisitions	Source
STEAM Education – Scientific and Technological Awareness	- Analyzing issues such as environmental pollution, climate change, and the conservation of natural resources using scientific methods.	Basic Law on the Education System. Law No. 46/86 (Government of Portugal, 1986)
	- Gaining awareness of the application of engineering principles and the development of environmentally friendly technologies.	Decree-Law no. 55/2018, of July 6. (Government of Portugal, 2018a)
STEAM Education – Mathematical Skills	- Developing the ability to draw meaningful conclusions from analyzing environmental data (such as air pollution, water quality, etc.), as well as enhancing data literacy and problem-solving skills.	Student Profile at the End of Compulsory Schooling. (Government of Portugal, 2017) Decree-Law no. 55/2018, of July 6. (Government of Portugal, 2018a)
STEAM Education – Art and Creativity	- Designing creative projects with recyclable materials to enhance environmental awareness and artistic sensitivity.	Basic Law on the Education System. Law No. 46/86 (Government of Portugal, 1986)
STEAM Education – Sustainability and Technology	- Evaluating the effects of science and technology on the environment and developing attitudes towards producing sustainable solutions.	National Strategy for Citizenship Education (Government of Portugal, 2025) Decree-Law no. 55/2018, of July 6. (Government of Portugal, 2018a)
Environmental Ethics – Respect for Nature and Responsibility	- Developing a sense of responsibility towards nature to approach environmental issues with an ethical perspective.	National Strategy for Citizenship Education (Government of Portugal, 2025) National Strategy for Environmental Education (Portuguese Environment Agency (APA), 2020)

		Basic Law on the Education System. Law No. 46/86 (Government of Portugal, 1986)
Environmental Ethics – Local and Global Environmental Problems	- Understanding local and global environmental issues (e.g., climate change, biodiversity loss) and developing solutions to address these problems	Basic Law on the Education System. Law No. 46/86 (Government of Portugal, 1986)
Environmental Ethics – Environmental Risk Prevention	- Gaining awareness of preventing and managing environmental risks, and being able to conduct sustainability-focused risk analysis.	National Strategy for Environmental Education (Portuguese Environment Agency (APA), 2020) National Strategy for Environmental Education (Portuguese Environment Agency (APA), 2020)
Environmental Ethics – Ethical Decision Making	- Gaining the ability to make decisions and establish attitudes while considering ethical values related to environmental issues	National Strategy for Citizenship Education (Government of Portugal, 2025) National Strategy for Environmental Education (Portuguese Environment Agency (APA), 2020)
General Curriculum Framework – Digitalisation in Education	- The development of digital skills for the purpose of collecting, sharing, and critically evaluating environmental data; the use of digital tools (sensors, data collection applications, etc.).	Action Plan for the Digital Transition of Portugal. (Government of Portugal, 2020) Decree-Law no. 55/2018, of July 6. (Government of Portugal, 2018a)
General Curriculum Framework – Sustainable Development	- Integrating sustainable development goals into curricula to instill environmental awareness and responsibility in students at both local and global levels.	National Strategy for Citizenship Education (Government of Portugal, 2025) National Strategy for Environmental Education (Portuguese Environment Agency (APA), 2020)

Decree-Law no. 55/2018, of July 6. ((Government of Portugal, 2018a)

General Curriculum Framework – Orientation to STEM Professions - Increasing the interest of female students in the fields of science and technology, encouraging their orientation towards STEM careers in the future, and ensuring equal opportunities in this area

Student Profile at the End of Compulsory Schooling. (Government of Portugal, 2017)

Decree-Law no. 55/2018, of July 6. (Government of Portugal, 2018a)
